

Synthesis of some lanthanide complexes with phenylalanine

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Fourteen complexes of lanthanide(III) ions with phenylalanine in presence of nitrate or perchlorate as counter anions have been synthesised in solid state. All these complexes have the general formulae $[\text{Ln}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{NO}_3)_3]$ and $[\text{Ln}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{ClO}_4)_2]\text{ClO}_4$, where Ln = La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Dy and Y, and Phe = phenylalanine.

Phenylalanine is an amino acid found in mammals and is utilized in the formation of hormones and the pigment, melanin¹. A search through the literature has revealed that very few solid complexes have been isolated so far². Phenylalanine exists predominantly in zwitterionic form. It has two potential donor sites, viz. the carbonyl oxygen and the amino nitrogen, and hence, it can form stable complexes with metal ions. We report here the synthesis of lanthanide complexes with phenylalanine in presence of nitrate or perchlorate ions and the coordination behaviour of phenylalanine towards the lanthanides.

Results and Discussion

The solid complexes of lanthanide nitrates and perchlorates with phenylalanine (Table 1) are non-hygroscopic. They are moderately soluble in acetonitrile, nitrobenzene and methanol, and insoluble in benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, diethyl ether and petroleum

ether. Molar conductance values of the complexes at room temperature ($28 \pm 2^\circ$) show that all the nitrate complexes are non-electrolytes, while all the perchlorate complexes behave as 1:1 electrolytes in these solvents³. Analytical and conductance data of the complexes suggest the following general formulae $[\text{Ln}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{NO}_3)_3]$ and $[\text{Ln}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{ClO}_4)_2]\text{ClO}_4$, where Ln = La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Dy and Y, and Phe = phenylalanine.

The observed magnetic moments of these complexes (Table 1) are comparable with the theoretical values calculated for the free metal ions using the Van Vleck formula⁴. The data indicate that the 4f-orbitals of the lanthanide ions are not involved in bonding in the present complexes.

The IR spectrum of phenylalanine exhibits a broad strong band at 3060 cm^{-1} attributed to νNH_3^+ mode of ligand existing as zwitterion. Two ligand bands at 2500 and 2100 cm^{-1} are assigned to overtone and combination bands

Table 1 Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Compd	Analysis % Found/(Calcd)		Mol cond ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in			μ_{eff} (B.M.) Found/ (Calcd)
	Metal	Nitrate/Perchlorate	Acetonitrile	Nitrobenzene	Methanol	
$[\text{La}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	16.9 (16.8)	22.6 (22.7)	43	1.5	59	0.00 (0.00)
$[\text{Pr}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	17.1 (16.4)	22.5 (22.6)	26	2.6	45	3.62 (3.61)
$[\text{Nd}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	17.5 (17.4)	22.5 (22.5)	52	1.9	55	3.68 (3.66)
$[\text{Sm}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	18.1 (18.6)	22.3 (22.4)	25	1.6	60	1.60 (1.57)
$[\text{Gd}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	18.7 (18.9)	22.1 (22.2)	60	2.5	65	7.96 (7.98)
$[\text{Dy}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	19.3 (19.1)	22.0 (22.1)	55	2.8	48	10.60 (10.57)
$[\text{Y}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	11.5 (11.4)	24.1 (24.1)	62	2.1	56	0.00 (0.00)
$[\text{La}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{ClO}_4)_2]\text{ClO}_4$	14.4 (14.1)	31.9 (32.0)	135	23	99	0.00 (0.00)
$[\text{Pr}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{ClO}_4)_2]\text{ClO}_4$	15.5 (15.1)	32.1 (31.9)	140	25	105	3.62 (3.61)
$[\text{Nd}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{ClO}_4)_2]\text{ClO}_4$	15.2 (15.4)	31.7 (31.8)	138	29	98	3.68 (3.67)
$[\text{Sm}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{ClO}_4)_2]\text{ClO}_4$	16.7 (15.9)	31.5 (31.6)	145	24	102	1.60 (1.66)
$[\text{Gd}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{ClO}_4)_2]\text{ClO}_4$	16.8 (16.9)	32.2 (32.2)	142	25	110	7.94 (7.98)
$[\text{Dy}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{ClO}_4)_2]\text{ClO}_4$	18.1 (17.4)	32.1 (32.0)	145	24	105	10.60 (10.58)
$[\text{Y}(\text{Phe})_3(\text{ClO}_4)_2]\text{ClO}_4$	10.5 (10.1)	33.7 (33.8)	140	28	101	0.00 (0.00)

* All nitrate complexes gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

of NH_3^+ vibrations. In the spectra of the complexes all the above three bands are absent. Instead, they exhibit two new strong bands at 3400 (OH of COOH) and 3090 cm^{-1} (NH). The positions of these bands are at lower than usually expected, which suggests that both carboxylic acid and amino groups of phenylalanine are coordinated to the lanthanide ions. Coordination of carboxylic acid group is further supported by the shifts of ν_{aCOO} and ν_{sCOO} , which are observed at 1650 and 1370 cm^{-1} , respectively. In the ligand these two bands appear at 1560 and 1390 cm^{-1} , respectively.

IR spectra of the lanthanide nitrate complexes exhibit three additional bands at 1460 , 1320 and 1020 cm^{-1} , which are attributed to coordinated nitrate groups, and are assigned to ν_4 , ν_1 and ν_2 modes, respectively. In fact, the bands due to ν_4 and ν_1 are the split bands of the originally degenerate ν_3 band of nitrate groups upon coordination. As the separation between the ν_4 and ν_1 bands is $\sim 140\text{ cm}^{-1}$, it is ascertained that the nitrate ions are coordinated unidentately to the lanthanide ions in the present complexes⁵. Coordination of all the three nitrate ions is also supported by the conductance values.

IR spectra of the lanthanide perchlorate complexes exhibit five additional bands at 1130 , 1100 , 1080 , 920 and 610 cm^{-1} , which are not present in the spectrum of the ligand. The strong bands at 1130 and 1080 cm^{-1} are the split bands of ν_3 mode of perchlorate ion upon coordination and that at 1100 cm^{-1} is attributed to ν_3 mode of uncoordinated perchlorate ion. The other two bands at 920 and 610 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_2 and ν_6 modes of perchlorate ion, respectively. Since the spectra of the complexes have split and unsplit bands of ν_3 mode, it is assumed that there are coordinated and uncoordinated perchlorate ions in the present complexes. The molar conductance values of the complexes in different solvents corresponding to 1 : 1 electrolytes (Table 1), suggest that two of the three perchlorate ions are coordinated and the third one remains ionic.

There are two additional bands in the spectra of all the complexes at 470 and 410 cm^{-1} , which are assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ln-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Ln-O}}$ modes, respectively. The presence of these two bands supports the coordination of carboxylic acid and amino groups of phenylalanine in the present complexes. Thus, from the above observations it is ascertained that each of the lanthanide ions has a coordination number 9 for the nitrate complexes and 8 for the perchlorate complexes. The exact structures could be obtained only from the single crystal X-ray studies, which could not be done due to lack of facilities and insolubility of the complexes in common solvents to warrant their crystallization.

Experimental

Nitrates and perchlorates of trivalent La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Dy and Y were prepared from the respective oxides by treating them with nitric acid and perchloric acid, respectively⁶. Phenylalanine (Sigma) was used as such.

The complexes of lanthanide nitrates and perchlorates with phenylalanine were prepared by a common procedure. Ethanolic solution of lanthanide nitrate or lanthanide perchlorate ($\sim 0.5\text{ g}$ in 50 ml of ethanol; 1.14 or 0.81 mmol) was mixed with phenylalanine ($\sim 0.57\text{ g}$; 3.45 mmol for the nitrate complexes or $\sim 0.4\text{ g}$; 2.42 mmol for the perchlorate complexes) followed by the addition of ethanol (50 ml). The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 10 – 12 h . The resulting solution was filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to get a viscous mass, which was washed with petroleum ether (10 ml each, 3 – 4 times) and the resulting solid lanthanide complexes were dried under reduced pressure over phosphorus pentoxide.

The lanthanide contents of the complexes were determined gravimetrically by the oxalate-oxide method⁷, nitrate using nitron reagent⁸ and perchlorate by the Kurz method⁹. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. Conductivity was measured on an Elico CM 82T conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature using a Gouy balance. The elemental analysis was performed at the National Chemical Laboratory, Pune.

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